

Coconut trees (called palms) grow flowers, and when these flowers are pollinated, they become coconuts. In nature, wind and insects help with this. But sometimes farmers want to choose which palm gives pollen and which one receives it. This is called hand pollination. It helps to produce better coconut seednuts for planting or selling.

This work can be done using simple tools. You do not need machines or expensive materials.

1. Why use hand pollination?

Sometimes, natural pollination is not enough. When a coconut seednut comes from natural pollination, you know its mother palm, but you don't know its father. The result of breeding is often very different from what we expect.

Hand pollination may help to produce true-to-type seednuts, especially when improving local varieties or creating new coconut hybrids.

Also, farmers may want to combine good traits from two different palms. For example, one palm gives many coconuts, and another rapidly produces nuts, or resists disease. Mixing them can give better future palms.

2. Three ways of bagging female flowers

Another sheet in this series describes the inflorescences and how coconut palms reproduce. Before pollination, female flowers must be isolated to exclude unwanted pollen. This is done just before the flower becomes receptive. There are three main ways:

1. Cover individual female flowers
2. Cover one spikelet (a branch of the inflorescence)
3. Cover the whole inflorescence

This sheet focuses on methods 1 and 3, the most useful in farm conditions.

3. Bagging single female flowers

In this case, the sacs are small cone-shaped caps that are placed on the female flower to isolate its tip. These tiny bags can be made of fabric, paper or even plant fragments. You can even use cone-shaped dried flowers, like bags already made by nature. Two male flowers, from the variety chosen as the father, are placed at the end of the cone.

Methods for bagging female flowers

Inflorescence

Covering the flower cluster for comprehensive protection

Individual flowers

Covering each flower separately for protection

Spikelet

Covering a branch of flowers for isolation

Controlled pollination process timeline

Use a male flower that has just opened and the other that is still closed and that is opened by gently pressing it.

Then, in the morning, mark the female flowers that appear will become receptive during the day. The small cones containing the two male flowers are placed on top of the female flowers. Normally fertilisation occurs during the day or the next day.

4. Bagging the whole inflorescence

This method is better when you want to pollinate many female flowers at once. In this case, you will have to prepare a breathable bag made of light cloth or non-woven fabric. Some supermarket bags are well adapted to this task. If possible, add glued plastic transparent windows to these bags, and apply this technique:

1. Open the envelope of the inflorescence, if possible one or two days before the date of its natural opening.
2. Remove and destroy/carry away all male flowers (emasculation) to avoid uncontrolled self-pollination.

3. Then, fix the bag and isolate the whole inflorescence.
4. Collect pollen from selected male flowers using clean tools. Mix this pollen with talcum powder or flour.
5. As soon as female flowers become receptive, introduce the pollen into the bag through a small hole using a squeeze bottle, or a sprayer.
6. Repeat the pollination every two days until all the tips of the female flowers turn blackish.

5. Tagging and quality controls

These precious seednuts will not be available until about a year after pollination. It is important to permanently mark the nuts well to remember precisely where to find them again. This marking will also be used to carry out quality controls, such as the number of coconuts obtained per bag. Other controls will be carried out later in the nursery, by observing the sprout colour and recording the germination rate.

For more details, see the full manual available online. Scan the QR code, or follow this link:
<https://www.spc.int/digitalibrary/get/wk5u9>

